

Annex E – Data reported on MRSA from food-producing animals and derived meat

Annex to:

EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) and ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control), 2025. The European Union Summary Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in zoonotic and indicator bacteria from humans, animals and food in 2023-2024.

Contents

Annex E – Data reported on MRSA from food-producing animals and derived meat	1
E.1 Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in food	3
Table 1: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in food, 2024.	3
Table 2: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in food, 2023.	5
E.2 Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in food-producing animals, clinical investigations excluded	7
Table 3: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in targeted food-producing animals, clinical investigations excluded, 2024.	7
Table 4: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in targeted food-producing animals, clinical investigations excluded, 2023.	9
E.3 Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in food-producing animals, clinical investigations	10
Table 5: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in targeted food-producing animals, clinical investigations, 2024.	10
E.4 Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in non-food-producing animals, clinical investigations.....	11
Table 6: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in targeted non-food-producing animals, clinical investigations, 2024.	11
Table 7: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in targeted non-food-producing animals, clinical investigations, 2023.	11
E.5 <i>spa</i> -type characterization in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	12
Table 8: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus spa</i>-type characterization, 2024.	12

Table 9: Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> spa-type characterization, 2023.	18
E.6 Occurrence of resistance to selected antimicrobials in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	21
Table 10: Occurrence of resistance (%) to selected antimicrobials in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> from food and animals, 2024.	21
Table 11: Occurrence of resistance (%) to selected antimicrobials in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> from food and animals, 2023.	22
Figure 1: Antimicrobial resistance in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> from targeted food-producing animals, 2023 and 2024.	23
Figure 2: Antimicrobial resistance in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> from food, 2023 and 2024.	24
E.7 MDR patterns in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	25
Table 12: MDR patterns in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> isolates from food and animals, 2024.	25
Table 13: MDR patterns in methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> isolates from food and animals, 2023.	31

E.1 Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in food

Table 1: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in food, 2024.

Food	Country	Production type/monitoring description (where specified)	Sample unit	Units tested	Units positive for MRSA (%)
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>)	Austria	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh - chilled	batch	325	15 (4.6%)
	Italy	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh - chilled	single	2	2 (100%)
	Norway	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	batch	325	0 (0%)
	Republic of North Macedonia	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh - chilled	single	4	0 (0%)
	Netherlands	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh - chilled	single	407	28 (6.9%)
	Germany	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcass	single	405	110 (27.2%)
	Germany	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh - chilled - border control post	single	26	0 (0%)
	Germany	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh - chilled - organic production	single	286	7 (2.4%)
	Germany	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh - chilled - conventional production	single	386	23 (6%)
Meat from turkey	Austria	Meat from turkey - fresh - chilled	batch	173	28 (16.2%)

Food	Country	Production type/monitoring description (where specified)	Sample unit	Units tested	Units positive for MRSA (%)
	Italy	Meat from turkey - fresh - chilled	single	1	1 (100%)
	Norway	Meat from turkey - fresh	batch	114	0 (0%)
	Netherlands	Meat from turkey - fresh - chilled	single	21	5 (23.8%)
	Germany	Meat from turkey - carcase	single	400	226 (56.5%)
	Germany	Meat from turkey - fresh - chilled	single	355	128 (36,1%)
Meat from bovine animals	Republic of North Macedonia	Meat from bovine animals - fresh - chilled	single	4	0 (0%)
	Netherlands	Meat from bovine animals - fresh	single	475	36 (7.6%)
Meat from pig	Republic of North Macedonia	Meat from pig - fresh - chilled	single	7	0 (0%)
	Netherlands	Meat from pig - fresh	single	279	22 (7.9%)
Meat from sheep	Netherlands	Meat from sheep - fresh	single	124	6 (4.8%)
	Netherlands	Meat from sheep - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	single	30	1 (3.3%)
Crustaceans	Germany	Crustaceans - unspecified - raw	single	226	40 (17.7%)
Meat from deer (venison)	Netherlands	Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - frozen	batch	18	0 (0%)
Meat from wild game - birds	Netherlands	Meat from wild game - birds - fresh	batch	4	0 (0%)

Table 2: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in food, 2023.

Food	Country	Production type/monitoring description (where specified)	Sample unit	Units tested	Positive for MRSA (%)
Meat from bovine animals	Austria	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	310	6 (1.9%) ^(a)
	Germany	Fresh - sampling at border control posts (monitoring)	Single	74	5 (6.8%) ^(b)
	Netherlands	Fresh - processing plant monitoring	Batch	184	25 (13.6%) *
	Netherlands	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	432	17 (3.9%) *
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>)	Netherlands	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	185	18 (9.7%) *
Meat from pigs	Austria	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	313	45 (14.4%) ^(c)
	Germany	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	380	39 (10.3%) ^(d)
	Netherlands	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	291	20 (6.9%) *
	Slovakia	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	130	20 (15.4%) *
Meat from turkey	Netherlands	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	7	2 (28.6%) *
Meat from deer (venison)	Netherlands	Fresh - sampling at border control posts (monitoring)	Batch	11	0 (0%)
Meat from duck	Netherlands	Fresh - sampling at border control posts (monitoring)	Batch	3	0 (0%)
Meat from farmed game - land mammals	Netherlands	Fresh - sampling at border control posts (monitoring)	Batch	3	0 (0%)
Meat from sheep	Netherlands	Fresh - retail monitoring	Single	151	7 (4.6%) *

Meat from wild game - birds	Netherlands	Fresh - sampling at border control posts (monitoring)	Batch	5	1 (20.0%) *
Prawns	Germany	Fresh - primary production monitoring	Single	10	0 (0%)

^(a) *spa*-types: t011 (3), t034 (3)

^(b) *spa*-types: t002 (4), t008 (1)

^(c) *spa*-types: t011 (20), t034 (12), t899 (1), t1255 (1), t1430 (3), t1451 (2), t2011 (4), t5524 (1), CC398, ST398 *spa*-type not reported (1)

^(d) *spa*-types: t008 (1), t011 (10), t034 (7), t127 (1), t693 (1), t899 (8), t1419 (1), t1430 (2), t1451 (1), t1580 (1), t2011 (2), t3512 (1), t20072 (1), *spa*-type not reported (2)

**spa*-types not reported

E.2 Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in food-producing animals, clinical investigations excluded

Table 3: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in targeted food-producing animals, clinical investigations excluded, 2024.

Animal	Country	Production type	Sample unit	Units tested	Positive for MRSA (%)
Cattle (bovine animals)	Belgium	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year) - veal calves	herd/flock	145	64 (44.1%)
	Belgium	Cattle (bovine animals) - dairy cows	herd/flock	126	12 (9.5%)
	Belgium	Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals	herd/flock	85	8 (9.4%)
	Netherlands	Cattle (bovine animals) - dairy cows	animal	674	0 (0%)
	Republic of North Macedonia	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	slaughter batch	13	0 (0%)
	Republic of North Macedonia	Cattle (bovine animals) - dairy cows	herd/flock	38	0 (0%)
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl)	Germany	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - broilers - before slaughter - conventional	single	261	3 (1.1%)
	Germany	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - broilers - before slaughter - organic	single	61	0 (0%)
	Norway	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl)	animal	325	0 (0%)
	Republic of North Macedonia	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - broilers - before slaughter	herd/flock	4	0 (0%)
Pigs	Netherlands	Pigs - fattening pigs	holding	114	81 (71.1%)
	Norway	Pigs - breeding animals	herd/flock	220	0 (0%)
	Norway	Pigs - fattening pigs	animal	27	0 (0%)

	Norway	Pigs - fattening pigs	herd/flock	2449	0 (0%)
	Republic of North Macedonia	Pigs - fattening pigs	herd/flock	24	0 (0%)
	Republic of North Macedonia	Pigs - fattening pigs	slaughter batch	12	0 (0%)
Turkeys	Norway	Turkeys - fattening flocks	animal	113	0 (0%)
Small ruminant	Portugal [#]	Goats	herd/flock	34	4 (11.7%)
	Portugal [#]	Sheep	herd/flock	72	4 (5.4%)

[#]Data retrieved from antimicrobial resistance isolate based data model.

Table 4: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in targeted food-producing animals, clinical investigations excluded, 2023.

Animal	Country	Production type	Sample unit	Units tested	Positive for MRSA (%)
Pigs	Norway	Pigs	herd/flock	541	0 (0%)
	Switzerland	Pigs - fattening pigs	animal	310	166 (53.5%)
	Slovakia	Pigs	animal	130	27 (20.8%)
	Germany	Pigs - breeding animals	herd/flock	351	91 (25.9%)
Cattle (bovine animals)	Netherlands	Cattle (bovine animals) - dairy cows	animal	316	2 (0.6%)
	Switzerland	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	animal	307	11 (3.6%)
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl)	Belgium	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - laying hens - adult	herd/flock	33	0 (0%)
	Belgium	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) - broilers - during rearing period	herd/flock	96	1 (1%)
Small ruminants	Netherlands	Sheep - meat production animals	herd/flock	156	8 (5.1%)
Turkeys	Belgium	Turkeys - fattening flocks	herd/flock	27	5 (18.5%)

E.3 Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in food-producing animals, clinical investigations

Table 5: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in targeted food-producing animals, clinical investigations, 2024.

Animal	Country	Production type	Sample unit	Units tested	Positive for MRSA (%)
Cattle	Norway	Cattle (bovine animals) – outbreak investigation	animal	69	13 (18.8%)
	Norway	Cattle (bovine animals) – outbreak investigation	herd/flock	69	27 (39.1%)
Pigs	Italy	Pigs	animal	1	1 (100%)
	Netherlands	Pigs - unspecified	animal	20	2 (10%)
	Norway	Pigs - mixed herds	animal	3	0 (0%)
	Norway	Pigs - mixed herds	herd/flock	2	0 (0%)
Small ruminants	Netherlands	Goats	animal	7	1 (14.3%)

E.4 Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in non-food-producing animals, clinical investigations

Table 66: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in targeted non-food-producing animals, clinical investigations, 2024.

Animal	Country	Production type	Sample unit	Units tested	Positive for MRSA (%)
Dogs	Norway	Dogs - pet animals	animal	4	0 (0%)
	Netherlands	Dogs - pet animals	animal	7447	10 (0.1%)
Felidae	Netherlands	Cats - pet animals	animal	2749	5 (0.2%)
	Norway	Cats - pet animals	Animal	1	0 (0%)
Land game mammals	Netherlands	Land game mammals - zoo animals	animal	470	16 (3.4%)
Solipeds, domestic	Netherlands	Solipeds, domestic - horses	animal	928	15 (1.6%)

Table 77: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in targeted non-food-producing animals, clinical investigations, 2023.

Animal	Country	Production type	Sample unit	Units tested	Positive for MRSA (%)
Dogs	Netherlands	Dogs	animal	7969	8 (0.1%)
Felidae	Netherlands	Cats - pet animals	animal	2883	3 (0.1%)
Solipeds, domestic	Netherlands	Solipeds, domestic - horses	animal	1028	13 (1.3%)

E.5 *spa*-type characterization in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

Table 88: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus spa*-type characterization, 2024.

Category	Country	Animal/food type	Sample type/unit	No. of isolates/ No. of samples tested	<i>spa</i> -type	ST	CC	Inferred CC*	LA, CA or HA type ^y	Inferred CC & type	<i>mec</i>	PVL status/ IEC genes
Food	Austria	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>)	Batch (food/feed)	5/325	34	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				2/325	11	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/325	330	45	45	-	-	CC45	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/325	330	9338	45	-	-	CC45	<i>mecA</i>	-
				2/325	899	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/325	127	1	1	-	LA	CC1/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/325	2	149	5	-	-	CC5	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/325	223	22	22	-	-	CC22	<i>mecA</i>	-
		1/325	843	130	-	-	-	-	<i>mecC</i>	-		
		Meat from turkey	Batch (food/feed)	13/173	11	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/173	11	5672	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	-	-
				6/173	34	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				5/173	899	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/173	1255	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
	1/173			127	1	1	-	LA	CC1/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-	
	1/173	8425	45	45	-	-	CC45	<i>mecA</i>	-			
	Germany	Meat from turkey - carcasses	Batch - slaughter animal	123/400	34	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				16/400	899	-	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				26/400	899	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-

Category	Country	Animal/food type	Sample type/ unit	No. of isolates/ No. of samples tested	spa-type	ST	CC	Inferred CC*	LA, CA or HA type [‡]	Inferred CC & type	mecA	PVL status/ IEC genes	
				27/400	11	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/400	3841	672	-	-	-	mecA	-		
				6/400	3841	-	-	-	-	mecA	-		
				4/400	1430	-	-	1	LA	CC1/LA	mecA	-	
				3/400	21298	-	-	-	-	mecA	-		
				3/400	6575	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				2/400	10485	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				2/400	8425	-	-	-	-	mecA	-		
				1/400	8588	-	-	-	-	mecA	-		
				1/400	8588	45	-	-	-	mecA	-		
				1/400	1255	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/400	1422	-	-	692	LA	CC692/LA	mecA	-	
				1/400	1451	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/400	693	-	-	-	LA	mecA	-		
		Meat from turkey - fresh meat		Batch (food/feed)	56/355	34	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
					13/355	899	-	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
					8/355	899	-	Non-398	1/398	LA	CC1/CC398 / LA	mecA	-
					15/355	11	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
					3/355	1451	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
					1/355	8425	45	45	-	-	CC45	mecA	-
1/355	8425	-	-	-	-	mecA	-						
1/355	10204	-	-	1	LA	CC1/LA	mecA	-					

Category	Country	Animal/food type	Sample type/ unit	No. of isolates/ No. of samples tested	spa-type	ST	CC	Inferred CC*	LA, CA or HA type [‡]	Inferred CC & type	mec	PVL status/ IEC genes
				1/355	127	-	-	1	LA	CC1/LA	mecA	-
				1/355	1430	-	-	1	LA	CC1/LA	mecA	-
				1/355	2	-	-	5	HA	CC5/HA	mecA	-
				1/355	3841	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
				1/355	8588	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
		Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>)-carcasses	Batch - slaughter animal	66/405	34	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
				28/405	11	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
				2/405	1344	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
				2/405	899	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
				1/405	12314	398	398	-	-	CC398/LA	mecA	-
				1/405	1606	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
				1/405	21298	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
				1/405	4132	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
				1/405	779	-	-	-	LA		mecA	-
		Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>)-fresh meat	Batch (food/feed) - conventional	1/286	6606	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
				1/286	11	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
				2/286	843	-	-	-	-		mecC	-
				2/286	899	-	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
			Batch (food/feed) - organic	1/386	2	-	-	5	HA	CC5/HA	mecA	-
				3/386	11	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-
				1/386	7	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
				1/386	12314	-	-	-	-		mecA	-
				8/386	34	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-

Category	Country	Animal/food type	Sample type/ unit	No. of isolates/ No. of samples tested	spa-type	ST	CC	Inferred CC*	LA, CA or HA type [‡]	Inferred CC & type	mec	PVL status/ IEC genes
		Crustaceans	Batch (food/feed)	7/226	304	-	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	304	6	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				5/226	127	-	-	1	LA	CC1/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				3/226	8	-	-	8	CA/HA	CC8/CA/HA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				2/226	189	-	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				2/226	5229	-	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	1219	6	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	1309	672	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	17387	8	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	1849	-	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	19	722	30	-	-	CC30	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	21860	1930	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	21897	1930	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	21999	80	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	22059	1232	398	-	-	CC398	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	309	22	22	-	-	CC22	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	34	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	376	-	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/226	45	-	-	-	-		<i>mecA</i>	-
1/226	8588	-	398	-	-	CC398	<i>mecA</i>	-				
Food-producing animals	Belgium	Calves	Herd/flock	49/145	11	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	-
				1/145	11	6035	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	<i>mecA</i>	<i>sak, scn</i>
				1/145	1344	398	398	-	-	CC398	<i>mecA</i>	-

Category	Country	Animal/food type	Sample type/unit	No. of isolates/ No. of samples tested	spa-type	ST	CC	Inferred CC*	LA, CA or HA type [‡]	Inferred CC & type	mec	PVL status/ IEC genes	
				2/145	1451	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/145	1606	398	398	-	-	CC398	mecA	-	
				5/145	2011	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/145	2346	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				3/145	2970	398	398	-	-	CC398	mecA	-	
				1/145	3423	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
		Diary cows	Herd/flock	10/126	11	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/126	588	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/126	1456	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
		Meat production animals (cattle)	Herd/flock	6/85	11	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/85	108	398	398	-	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
				1/85	177	9381	1	-	-	CC1	mecA	sak, scn	
	Germany	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl)	Herd/flock	3/261	34	-	-	398	LA	CC398/LA	mecA	-	
	Portugal [#]	Small ruminants (goats)	Herd/flock	1/34	3570	130	-	-	-	-		mecC	-
				1/34	3750	2328	-	-	-	-		-	-
				1/34	45	5	-	-	-	-		-	-
				1/34	3	6048	-	-	-	-		-	-
		Small ruminants (sheep)	Herd/flock	1/72	-	1640	-	-	-	-	-		-
1/72				108	398	-	-	LA		mecA	-		
1/72				3570	130	-	-	-	-		mecC	-	
1/72				22331	133	-	-	-	-		-	-	

CC, clonal complex; ST, sequence type; CA, community-associated; HA, hospital-associated; LA, livestock-associated; IEC, immune evasion cluster; PVL, Panton-Valentin leukocidin.

Details on the categorisation of *spa*-types can be found in the chapter on MRSA in the main part of the report (Section 6.3.3 Food and animals: Results of molecular typing of isolates). A summary of the information presented in this table is also visualised in Figure 60 of the MRSA chapter in the main part of the report.

*Data retrieved from antimicrobial resistance isolate based data model.

*For isolates where inferred CC is stated, the CC is based on the *spa*-type or ST as reported in literature:

- If ST and/or CC was not specified, *spa*-type t899 was classified as CC1/CC398 (EFSA, 2009; Guardabassi et al., 2009; Larsen et al., 2016).
- *spa*-types t011, t034, t108, t571, t588, t1255, t1451, t1456, t1580, t1793, t2011, t2330, t2346, t2576, t2922, t5452, t6228, t6575, t10485, t19248 were classified as CC398 (Battisti et al., 2010; EFSA 2009; Kinross et al., 2017; Köck et al., 2013; Pauly et al., 2019; Tkadlec et al., 2023).
- *spa*-type t127 was classified as CC1, LA-MRSA (EFSA, 2009; Merialdi et al., 2019).
- *spa*-types t002 and t242 were classified as CC5 (Asanin et al., 2019; Köck et al., 2013).
- *spa*-types t008 and t009 were classified as CC8 (Boost et al., 2012; Cuny et al., 2016).
- *spa*-types t1419, t1430 and t10204 were associated to ST9 (EFSA, 2009; Hasman et al., 2011; Köck et al., 2013) and classified as CC1 (PubMLST¹).
- *spa*-type t1422 was classified as CC692 (Silva et al., 2020).
- *spa*-type t3512 was classified as ST2343 (Chen et al., 2017) and CC1 (PubMLST¹).
- ST9 and ST8325 were classified as CC1 by PubMLST¹.
- ST22 was classified as CC22 by PubMLST¹*

^yIsolates with reported *spa* types were classified into their putative host association groups according to the following schedule:

- The following *spa* types were classified as: HA (Hospital associated): 2, 242, 20072
- The following *spa* types were classified as: CA/HA (Community or Hospital associated): 8, 9
- The following *spa* types were classified as: LA (Livestock associated): 11, 34, 108, 127, 235, 538, 571, 588, 693, 779, 899, 1255, 1419, 1422, 1430, 1451, 1456, 1457, 1580, 1793, 2011, 2330, 2346, 2576, 2922, 3075, 3423, 3512, 4652, 5104, 5452, 5524, 6228, 6575, 6608, 10204, 10485, 14089, 15528, 16666, 19248, 21217.

¹ https://pubmlst.org/bigsdb?db=pubmlst_saureus_seqdef&page=query

Table 99: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* spa-type characterization, 2023.

Category	Country	Animal/food type	Sample type/unit	No. of isolates	spa-type	PVL status/IEC genes	ST	CC	mec-gene	Inferred CC [‡]	LA, CA or HA	Inferred ST/CC & type
Food	Austria	Meat from cattle	Single, fresh, RM	2/310	11	-	398	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				3/310	34	-	398	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				1/310	11	-	-	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
		Meat from pigs	Single, fresh, RM	1/313	899	-	9	1	mecA		LA	CC1/LA
				3/313	1430	-	9	1	mecA		LA	CC1/LA
				19/313	11	-	398	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				12/313	34	-	398	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				2/313	1451	-	398	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				4/313	2011	-	398	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				1/313	5524	-	398	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				1/313	-	-	398	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				1/313	11	-	-	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				1/313	1255	-	-	398	mecA		LA	CC398/LA
				Germany	Meat from cattle	Single, fresh, BCP	4/74	2	-	-	-	mecA
	1/74	8	-				-	-	mecA	8	CA/HA	CC8/CA/HA
	Meat from pigs	Single, fresh, RM	1/380		693	-	9	-	mecA	1	LA	CC1/LA
			8/380		899	-	9	-	mecA	1	LA	CC1/LA
			1/380		20072	-	22	-	mecA	22	HA	CC22/HA
			1/380		8	-	-	-	mecA	8	CA/HA	CC8/CA/HA
	10/380	11	-	-	-	mecA	398	LA	CC398/LA			
7/380	34	-	-	-	mecA	398	LA	CC398/LA				

Category	Country	Animal/food type	Sample type/unit	No. of isolates	spa-type	PVL status/ IEC genes	ST	CC	<i>mecA</i> -gene	Inferred CC [‡]	LA, CA or HA	Inferred ST/CC & type
				1/380	127	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	1	LA	CC1/LA
				1/380	1419	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	1	LA	CC1/LA
				2/380	1430	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	1	LA	CC1/LA
				1/380	1451	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				1/380	1580	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				2/380	2011	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				1/380	3512	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	1	LA	CC1/LA
Food-producing animals	Belgium	Broilers	Flock, OFM	1/96	11	-	398	398	<i>mecA</i>	-	LA	CC398/LA
		Fattening turkeys	Flock, OFM	3/27	11	-	398	398	<i>mecA</i>	-	LA	CC398/LA
				2/27	11	-	873 1	398	<i>mecA</i>	-	LA	CC398/LA
	Germany	Breeding pigs	Herd, OFM	1/351	3075	-	398	398	<i>mecA</i>	-	LA	CC398/LA
				1/351	6608	-	398	398	<i>mecA</i>	-	LA	CC398/LA
				1/351	16666	-	398	398	<i>mecA</i>	-	LA	CC398/LA
				6/351	899	-	9	-	<i>mecA</i>	1	LA	CC1/LA
				19/351	11	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				38/351	34	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				1/351	108	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				2/351	1451	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				1/351	1456	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				6/351	2011	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
				2/351	2922	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA
1/351	4652	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA				
3/351	6575	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA				

Category	Country	Animal/food type	Sample type/unit	No. of isolates	spa-type	PVL status/IEC genes	ST	CC	mec-gene	Inferred CC [‡]	LA, CA or HA	Inferred ST/CC & type
				1/351	10204	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	1	LA	CC1/LA
				1/351	19248	-	-	-	<i>mecA</i>	398	LA	CC398/LA

OFM, on-farm monitoring; RM, retail monitoring; SM, slaughterhouse monitoring; BCP, border control post; CC, clonal complex; ST, sequence type; CA, community-associated; HA, hospital-associated; LA, livestock-associated; IEC, immune evasion cluster; PVL, Panton-Valentin leukocidin.

Details on the categorisation of *spa*-types can be found in the chapter on MRSA in the main part of the report (Section 6.3.3 Food and animals: Results of molecular typing of isolates). A summary of the information presented in this table is also visualised in Figure 60 of the MRSA chapter in the main part of the report.

*Hybrid strain, t899 can be associated with CC1 and CC398.

‡For isolates where “inferred CC is stated, the CC is based on the *spa*-type or ST as reported in literature.

E.6 Occurrence of resistance to selected antimicrobials in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

Table 1010: Occurrence of resistance (%) to selected antimicrobials in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from food and animals, 2024.

Country	N	GEN	KAN	STR	CHL	RIF	CIP	ERY	CLI	Q/D	LZD	TIA	MUP	FUS	SMX	TMP	TET	VAN	CEF	PEN
Meat from turkey																				
Germany	322	7.8	8.1	11.2	5.9	0.3	53.1	78.6	86.6	75.8	0.3	77.6	0.0	0.0	0.6	77.6	88.5	0	99.7	99.4
Austria	28	14.3	17.9	17.9	7.1	0.0	60.7	71.4	75.0	64.3	3.6	67.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	53.6	92.9	0	100.0	100.0
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>)																				
Germany	124	4.0	1.6	19.4	0.0	0.0	16.9	71.8	93.5	88.7	0.0	91.1	0.8	0.8	0.8	83.1	95.2	0	100.0	100.0
Austria	15	0.0	13.3	20.0	6.7	0.0	13.3	60.0	60.0	33.3	0.0	33.3	0.0	6.7	0.0	46.7	66.7	0	100.0	100.0
Crustaceans																				
Germany	34	32.4	35.3	0.0	5.9	0.0	47.1	82.4	23.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.8	0.0	29.4	23.5	0	100.0	100.0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl)																				
Germany	3	0.0	0.0	66.7	0.0	0.0	66.7	33.3	100.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0	100.0	66.7
Small ruminants																				
Portugal	8	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	12.5	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	62.5	0	100.0	37.5

N, number of isolates tested; GEN, gentamicin; KAN, kanamycin; STR, streptomycin; CHL, chloramphenicol; RIF, rifampicin; CIP, ciprofloxacin; ERY, erythromycin; CLI, clindamycin; Q/D, quinupristin/dalfopristin; LZD, linezolid; TIA, tiamulin; MUP, mupirocin; FUS, fusidic acid; SMX, sulfamethoxazole; TMP, trimethoprim; TET, tetracycline; VAN, vancomycin; CEF: ceftiofur; PEN; Penicillin

Table 1111: Occurrence of resistance (%) to selected antimicrobials in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from food and animals, 2023.

Country	N	GEN	KAN	STR	CHL	RIF	CIP	ERY	CLI	Q/D	LZD	TIA	MUP	FUS	SMX	TMP	TET	VAN
Cattle under 1 year																		
Switzerland	11	18.2	27.3	45.5	18.2	0	27.3	63.6	54.5	9.1	0	9.1	0	0	0	27.3	100	0
Pigs																		
Switzerland	166	7.8	10.4	30.1	25.9	0	41.0	25.3	41.6	39.8	0	39.2	0.6	0	0	41.0	95.2	0
Germany	84	6.0	6.0	26.2	3.6	1.2	28.6	56.0	79.8	58.3	0	61.9	0	0	1.2	73.8	95.2	0
Meat from pigs - fresh																		
Austria	45	4.4	4.4	24.4	4.4	4.4	33.3	37.8	53.3	37.8	0	35.6	0	0	2.2	42.2	91.1	0
Germany	37	16.2	10.8	16.2	8.1	0	40.5	59.5	56.8	27.0	0	27.0	0	0	0	54.1	70.3	0
Meat from cattle under 1 year - fresh																		
Austria	6 ^(d)	0	0	0	0	0	33.3	50.0	100	66.7	0	66.7	0	0	0	88.3	66.7	0
Germany	5 ^(e)	80.0	80.0	0	0	0	20.0	20.0	20.0	0	0	20.0	0	0	0	0	20.0	0

N, number of isolates tested; GEN, gentamicin; KAN, kanamycin; STR, streptomycin; CHL, chloramphenicol; RIF, rifampicin; CIP, ciprofloxacin; ERY, erythromycin; CLI, clindamycin; Q/D, quinupristin/dalfopristin; LZD, linezolid; TIA, tiamulin; MUP, mupirocin; FUS, fusidic acid; SMX, sulfamethoxazole; TMP, trimethoprim; TET, tetracycline; VAN, vancomycin. All MRSA isolates were resistant to penicillin and ceftiofur.

Figure 1: Antimicrobial resistance in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from targeted food-producing animals, 2023 and 2024.

CH: Switzerland, DE: Germany. In 2023, all isolates were resistant to CEF and PEN. In 2024, six isolates (Germany and Portugal) were susceptible to penicillin.

Figure 2: Antimicrobial resistance in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from food, 2023 and 2024.

AT: Austria, DE: Germany. In 2023, all isolates were resistant to penicillin and cefoxitin. In 2024, one German isolate was susceptible to cefoxitin and two to penicillin.

E.7 MDR patterns in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

Table 1212: MDR patterns in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from food and animals, 2024.

MDR patterns in MRSA isolates	Germany				Portugal	Austria		
	Meat from turkey (N=322)	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) (N=122)	Crustaceans (N=31)	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl) (N=3)	Small ruminants (N=3)	Meat from turkey (N=28)	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) (N=14)	Total
	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	90 (28)	61 (50)		1 (33.3)		4 (14.3)	2 (14.3)	158 (30.2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	74 (23)	3 (2.5)				5 (17.9)		82 (15.7)
CEF-CLI-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	11 (3.4)	10 (8.2)					1 (7.1)	22 (4.2)
CEF-CIP-PEN	17 (5.3)	1 (0.8)	2 (6.5)					20 (3.8)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA	5 (1.6)	10 (8.2)						15 (2.9)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP	12 (3.7)					2 (7.1)		14 (2.7)
CEF-CIP-CLI-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	1 (0.3)	12 (9.8)		1 (33.3)				14 (2.7)

CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	8 (2.5)	5 (4.1)						13 (2.5)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA	5 (1.6)	1 (0.8)				6 (21.4)		12 (2.3)
CEF-ERY-PEN			7 (22.6)				2 (14.3)	9 (1.7)
CEF-PEN-TET	3 (0.9)	3 (2.5)			1 (33.3)	2 (7.1)		9 (1.7)
CEF-CIP-PEN-TMP	8 (2.5)							8 (1.5)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	6 (1.9)	1 (0.8)						7 (1.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	7 (2.2)							7 (1.3)
CEF-CLI-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA	4 (1.2)	2 (1.6)					1 (7.1)	7 (1.3)
CEF-CLI-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (0.6)	2 (1.6)				1 (3.6)	1 (7.1)	6 (1.1)
CEF-CHL-PEN	4 (1.2)					1 (3.6)		5 (1)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA	4 (1.2)					1 (3.6)		5 (1)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET-TMP	2 (0.6)	2 (1.6)					1 (7.1)	5 (1)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET	1 (0.3)		3 (9.7)			1 (3.6)		5 (1)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-STR-TET	4 (1.2)							4 (0.8)
CEF-CIP-ERY-FUS-GEN-KAN-PEN			4 (12.9)					4 (0.8)
CEF-CIP-ERY-PEN			4 (12.9)					4 (0.8)
CEF-CIP-PEN-TET-TIA-TMP	3 (0.9)					1 (3.6)		4 (0.8)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	3 (0.9)							3 (0.6)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-PEN-Q/D-		3 (2.5)						3 (0.6)

STR-TET-TIA-TMP								
CEF-CLI-ERY-KAN-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	3 (0.9)							3 (0.6)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP			2 (6.5)					2 (0.4)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CHL-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TMP			2 (6.5)					2 (0.4)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TMP	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET	1 (0.3)						1 (7.1)	2 (0.4)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CIP-PEN-TET	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-PEN-TET	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET	2 (0.6)							2 (0.4)
CEF-ERY-KAN-PEN-STR	1 (0.3)					1 (3.6)		2 (0.4)
CEF-ERY-KAN-PEN-STR-TET	1 (0.3)						1 (7.1)	2 (0.4)
CEF-PEN-TMP			1 (3.2)				1 (7.1)	2 (0.4)

CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-ERY-KAN-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-LZD-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP						1 (3.6)		1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-LZD-PEN-Q/D-TIA	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-PEN-Q/D-TIA	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-PEN-TET-TIA					1 (33.3)			1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-PEN-TIA	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CIP-PEN	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CIP-PEN-STR	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-CLI-ERY-PEN-STR-TET							1 (7.1)	1 (0.2)
CEF-CHL-TET					1 (33.3)			1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-RIF-TET-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-SMX-TET-TIA-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-SMX-TET-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)

CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-TET-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-PEN-TIA	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP				1 (33.3)				1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TMP			1 (3.2)					1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-ERY-PEN-TMP			1 (3.2)					1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP						1 (3.6)		1 (0.2)
CEF-CIP-PEN-SMX-TET-TIA-TMP		1 (0.8)						1 (0.2)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN		1 (0.8)						1 (0.2)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-STR-TET-TMP		1 (0.8)						1 (0.2)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP			1 (3.2)					1 (0.2)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-PEN-TET-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CLI-ERY-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP							1 (7.1)	1 (0.2)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET-TIA	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-CLI-PEN-TET-TIA-TMP		1 (0.8)						1 (0.2)
CEF-CLI-PEN-TIA-TMP		1 (0.8)						1 (0.2)
CEF-ERY-FUS-MUP-PEN		1 (0.8)						1 (0.2)
CEF-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN			1 (3.2)					1 (0.2)
CEF-ERY-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP			1 (3.2)					1 (0.2)
CEF-ERY-PEN-TET-TIA-TMP	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CEF-ERY-PEN-TET-TMP			1 (3.2)					1 (0.2)
CEF-FUS-PEN							1 (7.1)	1 (0.2)

CEF-PEN-STR-TET						1 (3.6)		1 (0.2)
CEF-PEN-TET-TIA	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)
CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA	1 (0.3)							1 (0.2)

MDR, multidrug resistant; N, total number of isolates tested; n, number of isolates with MDR pattern; CEF, ceftiofur; PNC, penicillin; GEN, gentamicin; KAN, kanamycin; STR, streptomycin; CHL, chloramphenicol; RIF, rifampicin; CIP, ciprofloxacin; ERY, erythromycin; CLI, clindamycin; Q/D, quinupristin/dalfopristin; TIA, tiamulin; SMX, sulfamethoxazole; TMP, trimethoprim; TET, tetracycline.

Table 1313: MDR patterns in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from food and animals, 2023.

MDR patterns in MRSA isolates	Germany			Switzerland		Austria		
	Pigs (N=84)	Meat from bovine animals (N=4)	Meat from pig (N=37)	Cattle (bovine animals) (N=11)	Pigs (N=166)	Meat from pig (N=45)	Meat from bovine animals (N=6)	Total
	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)	n (% of MDR isolates)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	16 (19)		5 (13.5)	1 (9.1)	19 (11.4)	2 (4.4)		43 (12.2)
CEF-PEN-TET	6 (7.1)		2 (5.4)	1 (9.1)	14 (8.4)	9 (20)		32 (9.1)
CEF-CHL-CIP-PEN-TET					31 (18.7)			31 (8.8)
CEF-CLI-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	10 (11.9)				10 (6)	2 (4.4)	1 (16.7)	23 (6.5)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	4 (4.8)		2 (5.4)		14 (8.4)			20 (5.7)
CEF-PEN-STR-TET	1 (1.2)			1 (9.1)	14 (8.4)	2 (4.4)		18 (5.1)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET-TMP	5 (6)		4 (10.8)	1 (9.1)			1 (16.7)	11 (3.1)
CEF-CIP-PEN			7 (18.9)			4 (8.9)		11 (3.1)

CEF-CIP-PEN-TET	1 (1.2)		1 (2.7)		7 (4.2)	2 (4.4)		11 (3.1)
CEF-CLI-PEN-Q/D-TIA-TMP					8 (4.8)		2 (33.3)	10 (2.8)
CEF-CLI-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	5 (6)				1 (0.6)	3 (6.7)		9 (2.5)
CEF-CIP-CLI-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (2.4)				4 (2.4)	1 (2.2)		7 (2)
CEF-CIP-PEN-STR-TET					7 (4.2)			7 (2)
CEF-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET				1 (9.1)	6 (3.6)			7 (2)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (2.4)				1 (0.6)	2 (4.4)	1 (16.7)	6 (1.7)
CEF-PEN-TET-TMP			2 (5.4)		4 (2.4)			6 (1.7)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (2.4)		1 (2.7)		1 (0.6)	1 (2.2)		5 (1.4)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA	3 (3.6)		1 (2.7)			1 (2.2)		5 (1.4)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET	1 (1.2)				3 (1.8)			4 (1.1)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET	1 (1.2)			1 (9.1)		1 (2.2)	1 (16.7)	4 (1.1)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-KAN-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA					3 (1.8)			3 (0.8)
CEF-CHL-CIP-PEN-STR-TET					3 (1.8)			3 (0.8)

CEF-CIP-PEN-TET-TMP					2 (1.2)	1 (2.2)		3 (0.8)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)		2 (5.4)					3 (0.8)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-PEN-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)		1 (2.7)			1 (2.2)		3 (0.8)
CEF-GEN-KAN-PEN		3 (75)						3 (0.8)
CEF-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)			1 (9.1)	1 (0.6)			3 (0.8)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-STR-TET				2 (18.2)				2 (0.6)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET					2 (1.2)			2 (0.6)
CEF-CHL-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)					1 (2.2)		2 (0.6)
CEF-CHL-PEN-TET			1 (2.7)			1 (2.2)		2 (0.6)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN	1 (1.2)		1 (2.7)					2 (0.6)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-STR-TET						2 (4.4)		2 (0.6)
CEF-CIP-CLI-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA-TMP	2 (2.4)							2 (0.6)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-STR-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)					1 (2.2)		2 (0.6)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)					1 (2.2)		2 (0.6)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-STR-TET	1 (1.2)			1 (9.1)				2 (0.6)

CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)					1 (2.2)		2 (0.6)
CEF-PEN-TET-TIA	2 (2.4)							2 (0.6)
CEF-CHL-CIP-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA					1 (0.6)			1 (0.3)
CEF-CHL-CIP-KAN-PEN-TET					1 (0.6)			1 (0.3)
CEF-CHL-CIP-MUP-PEN-TET					1 (0.6)			1 (0.3)
CEF-CHL-CIP-PEN-STR-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CHL-CIP-PEN-TMP	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CHL-CLI-ERY-GEN-PEN-TET-TMP			1 (2.7)					1 (0.3)
CEF-CHL-CLI-ERY-KAN-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA			1 (2.7)					1 (0.3)
CEF-CHL-PEN-STR-TET					1 (0.6)			1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-GEN-KAN-PEN-TET-TIA		1 (25)						1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-KAN-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP						1 (2.2)		1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-RIF-TET-TIA	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)

CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA						1 (2.2)		1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-STR	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-STR-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-ERY-PEN-TET	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-KAN-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA-TMP						1 (0.6)		1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-CLI-PEN-TET-TMP						1 (0.6)		1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-GEN-PEN-TET						1 (0.6)		1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-KAN-PEN-STR-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-PEN-Q/D-TET						1 (0.6)		1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-PEN-SMX	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-PEN-STR			1 (2.7)					1 (0.3)
CEF-CIP-PEN-STR-TET-TMP	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-PEN-STR-TET-TMP			1 (2.7)					1 (0.3)
CEF-CLI-ERY-GEN-PEN-TET			1 (2.7)					1 (0.3)

CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-RIF-TET-TIA-TMP						1 (2.2)		1 (0.3)
CEF-CLI-ERY-PEN-Q/D-STR-TET-TIA	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-CLI-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA						1 (2.2)		1 (0.3)
CEF-CLI-PEN-TET-TIA-TMP	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-ERY-KAN-PEN			1 (2.7)					1 (0.3)
CEF-ERY-KAN-PEN-STR-TET				1 (9.1)				1 (0.3)
CEF-ERY-PEN-TET-TIA-TMP					1 (0.6)			1 (0.3)
CEF-GEN-KAN-PEN-Q/D-TET-TIA					1 (0.6)			1 (0.3)
CEF-PEN-Q/D-TET					1 (0.6)			1 (0.3)
CEF-PEN-RIF-TET						1 (2.2)		1 (0.3)
CEF-PEN-SMX-TET						1 (2.2)		1 (0.3)
CEF-PEN-TET-TIA-TMP	1 (1.2)							1 (0.3)
CEF-PEN-TMP			1 (2.7)					1 (0.3)

MDR, multidrug resistant; N, total number of isolates tested; n, number of isolates with MDR pattern; CEF, ceftiofur; PNC, penicillin; GEN, gentamicin; KAN, kanamycin; STR, streptomycin; CHL, chloramphenicol; RIF, rifampicin; CIP, ciprofloxacin; ERY, erythromycin; CLI, clindamycin; Q/D, quinupristin/dalfopristin; TIA, tiamulin; SMX, sulfamethoxazole; TMP, trimethoprim; TET, tetracycline.